

THE CORE CONCEPTS AND PRINCIPLES OF THE LINGUISTIC PICTURE THEORY

Mavluda Urozboeva Shukurlo qizi

UzSWLU, Teacher

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract

The theory of linguistic landscape, a key area in cognitive linguistics, explores the relationship between language and human cognition, focusing on how language reflects and shapes human perception and worldview. Unlike traditional linguistic approaches that view language merely as a system of rules and structures, the theory of linguistic landscape emphasizes the role of language in constructing and organizing our understanding of the world. Grammatical categories, such as time, space, and action, are seen not only as structural elements but also as cognitive tools that reveal how humans perceive and categorize their surroundings. This paper discusses the main concepts and principles of the linguistic landscape theory, examining the interconnection between language, cognition, and culture. It highlights the importance of grammatical categories in forming the meaning and structure of language, showcasing how they reflect not only individual cognition but also social and cultural values.

Keywords: *Linguistic landscape, cognitive linguistics, grammatical categories, worldview, perception, language and cognition, cultural values, meaning formation, language structure, time, space, action, social context.*

Introduction

The theory of the linguistic landscape of the world is a scientific direction that studies the complex relationship between language and human thought. This theory emphasizes that language is not only a means of communication, but also a force that shapes how people view, think, and perceive their environment. Through

language, we understand how we imagine ourselves and the world around us, based on which categories and structures we perceive life. Our worldview and ideas about the world are expressed through language. Each language creates its own image of the world, and this image is closely related to the culture, social experience, historical context and imagination of the people who use the language. The theory of the linguistic landscape of the world analyzes how language shapes human thinking and how it forms a worldview based on it.

Main body

Based on the theory of the linguistic landscape of the world, language is not considered only as a collection of grammatical structures. Language, especially grammatical categories, are the foundations that shape a person's worldview. Grammar and semantics are seen as closely related, language-shaping forces. The basic structures of language, including words, phrases, and grammatical categories, not only make up the language system, but also help us create ideas about the world. Through language we can see how we imagine ourselves and the world around us. For example, concepts such as time, place, action, state are expressed in a unique way in each society, and these expressions are based on the grammatical and semantic structures of the language.

The categories of grammar depend on how we create and use language, and they are closely related to human thinking. For example, in some languages, the category of time not only indicates the time of occurrence of events, but also provides information about how the events will take place, their duration or completion. This shows how the person speaking the language has ideas about the world. The concepts of time and aspect (tense and aspect), which are one of the main grammatical categories of the language, are used not only to determine time, but with their help we can express the duration, repetition or completion of an action or event. These grammatical categories reflect human thinking about time, action, and events (Lakoff, 1987).

At the same time, the theory of the linguistic landscape of the world not only illuminates the thinking of individuals, but also studies their culture, social changes and values. According to this theory, grammatical categories in the language should be analyzed not only from a grammatical and syntactic point of view, but also from a cultural and social point of view. For example, in some languages gender categories (masculine, feminine) are grammatically distinct, which is a reflection of the gender roles and social structures in that society. The gender categories present in a language are not only a matter of grammar, but also reflect the cultural and social context. This shows how closely related language and culture are (Whorf, 1956).

Also, in the theory of the linguistic landscape of language, language is not only a set of grammatical structures, but also an element related to social and cultural changes. The grammatical categories available in a language change and these changes are based on the thinking, culture and historical experiences of the society. Through new words, phrases and grammatical structures in the language, society reflects its social and cultural changes. For example, new technologies and social inventions introduce new words and categories into the language, which reflect a new worldview of society. One of the unique features of language in the theory of the linguistic landscape of the world is that the language expresses the world view of a person not only individually, but collectively. The cultural and social role of language is that through language we express not only our personal experiences, but also the general thinking and values of our society. Through grammar and other structures of language, we can see the views of our society and culture.

Conclusion

The theory of the linguistic landscape of the world is a scientific direction aimed at the in-depth study of the interaction between language and human thinking. According to this theory, language is not only a means of communication,

but the main tool that shapes a person's worldview and thinking. Grammatical categories in the language reflect not only the internal structure of the language, but also the worldview, culture and social changes of the language users. Grammar and semantics study not only structural but also content aspects of language. Thus, the theory of the linguistic landscape of the world reveals the importance of language in the formation of human thinking and worldview. With this theory, the connection between language and thinking is better understood, and it is possible to better understand how we create ideas about the world through language.

Resources

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